

Glicol Workshop

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ABSTRACT

Glicol (an acronym for 'graph-oriented live coding language') is a computer music language and an audio DSP library written in Rust. Ever since its publication at Web Audio Conference 2021, it has attracted a considerable amount of attention around the world and it has been actively developed during the past few months.

There are two main directions for Glicol's road-map: one is to enhance the audio engine on the low level; the other is to map the audio engine to different high-level musical interactions such as collaborative live coding, education applications, and AI connection.

In the past year, Glicol has been rewritten from the low level. It can now be used as an NPM package or a Rust audio library and these all come with real-world examples. And on the high-level aspect, we invent a new mechanism for online collaborations based on the WYSIWYG (what you see is what you get) paradigm offered by the Glicol audio engine. We will also shed a light on how Glicol can be applied into the music education.

In this workshop, we will cover (1) how to use Glicol for music performance or music education, with a focus on online collaboration (<https://glicol.org>); (2) how to use Glicol as an NPM audio library for browsers (<https://glicol.js.org>).

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